

Synthesis, spectral and thermal studies of tin(IV) complexes using 2-benzimidazolylmercaptoaceto hydrazone type of ligands

V. M. Naik, S. K. Patil, S. B. Tallur and N. B. Mallur*

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003, Karnataka, India

E-mail : nayakvinu06@rediffmail.com; nirmalmallur@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 20 September 2007, accepted 26 September 2007

Abstract : The metal complexes of Sn^{IV} with 2-benzimidazolylmercaptoaceto hydrazones of 1 : 2 metal to ligand stoichiometry have been synthesized. Molar conductance data reveal their non-electrolytic nature. The spectral studies show that the ligands react in enol form and behave as dibasic tridentate ONO donor. The thermal stabilities of the complexes have been studied by TG and their kinetic parameters calculated using Coats-Redfern and MKN methods. From these results, a coordination number six for tin ion in the complexes of the type SnL₂ have been proposed.

Keywords : Tin(IV) complexes, hydrazones, kinetic, TG.

Introduction

A number of Sn^{IV} complexes with hydrazones containing a variety of donor sites have been reported¹, where the usual coordination number of the tin is six. Our interest is to study the ligating behaviour and stereochemical aspect of Sn^{IV} complexes derived from 2-benzimidazolylmercaptoaceto hydrazone type of ligands, LH₂ (1).

Results and discussion

The complexes were synthesized starting from tin tetrachloride and an ethanolic solution of the ligands, LH₂, in nitrogen atmosphere. They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Analytical data of all the yellow coloured Sn^{IV} complexes (Table 1) is consistent with 1 : 2 metal to ligand stoichiometry, thus they can be represented by the general formula SnL₂, which is indicative of the tridentate behaviour of the ligands. The conductance measurements in DMF reveal that they are essentially non-electrolytes.

The free ligands exhibit absorption bands at 288–303, 305–335 and 327–370 nm in the UV-Vis spectra. The complexes display bands at 245–280, 290–315 and 370–455 nm. The observed shifts of the ligand bands and the appearance of a new broad band at 370–455 nm considered as charge transfer transition in the spectra of Sn^{IV} complexes².

Infrared spectra :

The ligands show bands at 3240–3200 (NH of hydrazide), 3050–3010 (NH of imidazole), 1705–1685 (C=O), 1230–1218 (C–O), 1654–1648 (C=N)^{3–5} and 3445–3420 cm⁻¹ due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonded -OH. In the IR spectra of the Sn^{IV} complexes, the ν(C=O) modes are not observed suggesting the possibility of enolization of C=O followed by deprotonation and complexation with tin(IV). The ν(C=N) modes of ligands are found to shift to lower wave number, possibly due to coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the central metal ion. A noticeable change in the IR spectra

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of Sn^{IV} complexes

Complex Mol. formula	Abbreviation	Metal % :		Mol. conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
		Found	(Calcd.)	
Sn(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂	Sn(L ¹) ₂	15.54	(15.46)	6.45
Sn(C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SCI) ₂	Sn(L ²) ₂	13.98	(14.19)	9.05
Sn(C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SBr) ₂	Sn(L ³) ₂	12.90	(12.83)	9.12
Sn(C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂	Sn(L ⁴) ₂	15.03	(14.92)	7.84
Sn(C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S) ₂	Sn(L ⁵) ₂	14.11	(14.34)	5.02

*All complexes gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

of the complexes is the shift of $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) to higher energy side by $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating complex formation via deprotonation of phenolic $-\text{OH}$. The band at $555\text{--}528\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-N})$ vibrations^{6,7}. On the basis of the available data on the $\nu(\text{M-O})$ vibrations^{8,9}, the stretch at $460\text{--}452\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ vibrations.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectrum of ligand (L^2H_2) shows signals at δ 7.32–8.01 (m, ArH), 3.66 (CH_2), 8.66 (azomethine H), 12.05 (s, phenolic $-\text{OH}$), 11.02 (s, NH hydrazine) and 12.90 ppm (s, NH imidazole). In the complex the multiplet observed between 7.21–7.94 ppm is due to aromatic protons. The proton signal at 12.05 ppm due to phenolic $-\text{OH}$ has disappeared in the complex suggesting that the phenolic $-\text{OH}$ undergoes deprotonated during complexation. The shifting of azomethine proton to the downfield (δ 8.87) confirms involvement of azomethine

	$\text{L}^1\text{H}_2\text{--L}^5\text{H}_2$	
Ligand	R	R^1
L^1H_2	H	H
L^2H_2	Cl	H
L^3H_2	Br	H
L^4H_2	CH_3	H
L^5H_2	H	OCH_3

Structure of ligands (1)

nitrogen in coordination to the metal ion. The $-\text{NH}$ (hydrazine) signal which disappears in the complex, suggesting that the enolization of the ligand followed by deprotonation, prior to coordination of carbonyl oxygen to the metal ion. The singlet due to $-\text{NH}$ (imidazole) proton is unaffected in the spectrum of the Sn^{IV} complex. This indicates that $-\text{NH}$ (imidazole) group is not involved in coordination. All these data put together clearly suggests that the ligand is in enol form during coordination and acts as dibasic, tridentate donor.

Thermal studies :

The thermal behaviour of Sn^{IV} complexes, including

stability ranges, peak temperatures, percentage of weight loss, percentage of residue obtained after decomposition process using thermogravimetry has been studied. The Sn^{IV} complex undergoes decomposition in two stages.

Proposed structure of Sn^{IV} complexes (2)

The complex is stable upto $135\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as indicated by a plateau in TG curve. The complex registered the first decomposition occurs $135\text{--}315\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and DTG peak at $190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ represents this. The second stage of decomposition occurs at $315\text{--}605\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and is represented by a DTG peak at $384\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The total weight loss at the end of second stage (83.07%) corresponds to the loss of two molecules of ligands. This agrees well with the calculated value (84.52%). Beyond $605\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ a plateau is obtained which indicates the formation of stable oxide (SnO_2). The weight of the oxide (18.73%) agrees well with calculated value (19.64%). The percentage of metal calculated from the TG studies is in keeping with the theoretical results within the experimental errors.

The kinetic parameters the energy of activation, entropy of activation and pre-exponential factor are calculated using Coats-Redfern and MKN equations (Table 2). The thermal decomposition reactions of these complexes were studied using non-isothermal method. In the present complexes, the kinetic parameters such as energy of activation, entropy of activation and pre-exponential factor for all these clear-cut decomposition stages of the complex have been calculated using the Coats-Redfern and MKN equations by graphical as well as least square method (Fig. 1). The energy of activation values for the second stage decomposition of the complexes was found to be lower than those for the first stage decomposition. The lower value of energy of activation indicates an increased rate at this stage¹⁰.

The negative entropy of activation values for all degradation stages, shows that the complex is more ordered in the activated state through the chemisorption of oxy-

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of $\text{Sn(L}^1\text{)}_2$ using Coats-Redfern (MKN) equation

Decomposition stage	Energy of activation (E_a) [*] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Arrhenius factor (A) (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Correlation coefficient (r)
I	48.5812 (46.8196)	5.7486×10^5 (1.9747×10^5)	-139 (-148)	0.9901 (0.9934)
II	11.3827 (12.0354)	11.8442 (8.8707)	-231 (-234)	0.9993 (0.9961)

gen and other decomposition products¹¹. The negative entropy of activation values is compensated by the values of the energies of activation. The decrease in value of entropy of activation from first step to the second step indicates that the rate of decomposition increases in stepwise reactions.

Conclusions :

From the foregoing discussion it is concluded that the ligands react in an enol form with Sn^{IV} from the com-

plexes. Based upon analytical and spectral studies, the coordination number six for tin ion in the monomeric complexes of the type SnL_2 (2) have been proposed.

Experimental

The chemicals used were A.R. grade. The solvents were dried and distilled before use. 2-Mercaptobenzimidazole was prepared by using standard method¹². Tin was estimated as SnO_2 by gravimetric method. The elemental analyses (C, H and N) were analyzed on a Heraeus Carlo Erba-1108 instrument.

2-Benzimidazolylmercaptoacetohydrazide¹³ : To an absolute ethanolic solution (100 ml) containing sodium metal (2.8 g), 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (18.7 g) was added with stirring. The resulting mercaptide was slowly treated with ethyl chloroacetate (35–40 ml). The solution turned turbid and within a few minutes sodium chloride separated out. The mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for ~1 h and then filtered. The alcoholic solution was concentrated to about 50% of its original volume and hydrazine hydrate (15 ml) was added. The solution was refluxed for ~20 h on a steam bath and then cooled in ice. The separated solid was washed and crystallized from alcohol (yield 60%).

2-Benzimidazolylmercaptoacetohydrazone (LH_2) : To an ethanolic solution of 2-benzimidazolylmercaptoacetohydrazide (0.1 mol) was added salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde (0.1 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for ~3 h. The solution was filtered, the filtrate is concentrated and cooled. The separated solid was washed and crystallized from alcohol (yield 70–80%).

Tin(IV) complexes (SnL_2) : To a dry ethanolic solution of ligand (25 ml, 0.002 mol), tin tetrachloride (0.001 mol) dissolved in dry ethanol was added, the mixture was stirred and refluxed for ~1 h on a water-bath. The separated yellow coloured solid complex was washed with dry ethanol and dried over P_2O_5 (yield 65%).

Conductivity was measured (in DMF at 10^{-3} M) using

Fig. 1. Coats-Redfern plots for the two decomposition steps of $\text{Sn(L}^1\text{)}_2$.

a Elico conductivity bridge type CM-82 provided with a cell constant 0.51 cm^{-1} IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Impact 410-Nicolet FTIR spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) on a Bruker AC 300F (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. TG and DTG were carried out from room temperature to about $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in dynamic air atmosphere on a Rigaku-TAS-100 model thermal analyzer maintaining a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Kinetic parameters were computed from the thermal decomposition data.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad, for providing the facilities.

References

1. G. H. Havanur, V. K. Revankar and V. B. Mahale, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 803.
2. K. Dey, P. K. Bhattacharya, D. Bandyopadhyay, K. Chakraborty and A. K. Mallik, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 529
3. S. P. Ghosh and K. M. Prasad, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1963.
4. L. El-Sayed and N. F. Iskander, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 435.
5. B. R. Havinale and I. B. Pujar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 1042.
6. N. S. Biradar and V. H. Kulkarni, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **39**, 3847.
7. K. Nakamoto in "Advances in the Chemistry of Coordination Compounds", ed. S. Krischner, McMillan, New York, 1961
8. G. T. Behnke and K. Nakamoto, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 433.
9. R. W. Jones and R. C. Fay, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 2599.
10. P. B. Maravalli and T. R. Goudar, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1999, **35**, 325.
11. T. P. Hoar, "Pittsburg Intern. Conf. on Surface reactions", 1948, **127**.
12. J. A. Allan and B. D. Deacon, *Org. Synth.*, 1963, **4**, 569.
13. S. P. Singh, S. S. Parmar and B. R. Pandey, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1977, **14**, 1093.